

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 42:0 For the choir director. A †Maskil of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p>Psa. 42:1 לְמִנְצַח מִשְׁכִּיל לְבְנֵי־קֹרַח : 2 כְּאֵיל תִּעְרַג עַל־אֲפִיקַי־מַיִם כִּן נִפְשִׁי</p>
<p>Psa. 42:1 As the deer ¹pants for the water brooks, So my soul ^{1a}pants for You, O God.</p>	<p>תִּעְרַג אֵלַיךָ אֱלֹהִים : 3 צְמָאָה נִפְשִׁי לֵאלֹהִים לְאֵל</p>
<p>² My soul ^athirsts for God, for the ⁴living God; When shall I come and ^{1c}appear before God?</p>	<p>תִּי מָתִי אָבּוֹא וְאֶרְאֶה פָּנַי אֱלֹהִים : 4 הֲיִתָּה־לִּי דְמָעָתִי</p>
<p>³ My ^atears have been my food day and night, While <i>they</i> ^bsay to me all day long, “Where is your God?”</p>	<p>לֶחֶם יוֹמָם וְלַיְלָה בְּאֶמְר אֵלַי כָּל־הַיּוֹם אַיֶּה אֱלֹהֶיךָ :</p>
<p>⁴ These things I remember and I ^apour out my soul within me. For I ^bused to go along with the throng <i>and</i> ¹lead them in procession to the house of God, With the voice of ⁵joy and thanksgiving, a multitude keeping festival.</p>	<p>אֵלֶּה אֲזַכֵּרָה וְאֶשְׂפֹּכָה עָלַי וְנִפְשִׁי כִּי אֶעְבֵּר וּבִסְף־ אֲדִדָּם עַד־בַּיִת אֱלֹהִים בְּקוֹל־רִנָּה וְתוֹדָה הַמְּנוֹן חוֹנֵג : 6 מֵהַתְּשִׁיתוֹתַי </p>
<p>Psa. 42:5 ^aWhy are you ^{1b}in despair, O my soul? And <i>why</i> have you become ^cdisturbed within me?</p>	<p>נִפְשִׁי וְתַהַמְּי עָלַי הוֹתִילַי לֵאלֹהִים כִּי־עוֹד אוֹדֵנוּ יְשׁוּעוֹת פָּנִיו : 7 אֱלֹהֵי עָלִי</p>
<p>^{2d}Hope in God, for I shall ³again praise ⁴Him For the ^{5c}help of His presence. ⁶ O my God, my soul is ¹in despair within me; Therefore I ^aremember You from ^bthe land of the Jordan</p>	<p>נִפְשִׁי תְשִׁיתוֹת עַל־כֵּן אֲזַכֵּרָךְ מֵאֶרֶץ יַרְדֵּן וְחֶרְמוֹנִים מִתְּהַר מִצְעָר : 8</p>

And the ²peaks of ‘Hermon, from Mount Mizar.

⁷ Deep calls to deep at the sound of Your waterfalls;

All Your ^abreakers and Your waves have rolled over me.

⁸ The LORD will ^acommand His lovingkindness in the daytime;

And His song will be with me ^bin the night,

A prayer to ^cthe God of my life.

Psa. 42:9 I will say to God ^a“my rock, ^b“Why have You forgotten me?

Why do I go ^bmourning ¹because of the ^c“oppression of the enemy?”

¹⁰ As a shattering of my bones, my adversaries revile me,

While they ^asay to me all day long, ^b“Where is your God?”

¹¹ ^a“Why are you ¹in despair, O my soul?

And why have you become disturbed within me?

²Hope in God, for I shall yet praise Him,

The ³help of my countenance and my God.

תְּהוֹם-אֶל-תְּהוֹם קוֹרָא
לְקוֹל צְנוּרִיךָ כָּל-מִשְׁבְּרֵיךָ
וְגִלְיָךָ עָלַי עָבְרוּ: ⁹ יוֹמָם |
יִצְוֶה יְהוָה אֶת-סִדּוֹ וְיַבִּילֶנָּה
שִׁירָה [שִׁירוֹ] עִמִּי תִּפְלֶה
לְאֵל תִּי: ¹⁰ אֹמְרָה אֲלֵאל
סִלְעֵי לָמָּה שָׁכַחְתָּנִי לָמָּה-
קָדַר אֱלֹהֶיךָ בְּלַחֵץ אֹיִב: ¹¹
בְּרָצַח אֲבַעֲצָמוֹתַי תִּרְפוּנִי
צוּרֵי בְּאִמְרָם אֵלַי כָּל-
הַיּוֹם אֵינִי אֶלְהֵיךָ: ¹² מָה-
תִּשְׁתַּחֲוֶהֶנִּי אֲנִי וְנַפְשִׁי וְנִמָּה-
תִּהְיֶה עָלַי הוֹחֵלִי לְאֱלֹהִים
כִּי-עוֹד אֹדְנֵנוּ יְשׁוּעַת פָּנֵי
וְאֱלֹהֵי:

References

<p>Psalm 42:1 ¹Lit <i>longs for</i> ^aPs 119:131</p> <p>Psalm 42:2 ¹Some mss read <i>see the face of God</i> ^aPs 63:1; 84:2; 143:6 ^bJosh 3:10; Ps 84:2; Jer 10:10; Dan 6:26; Matt 26:63; Rom 9:26; 1 Thess 1:9 ^cEx 23:17; Ps 43:4; 84:7</p> <p>Psalm 42:3 ^aPs 80:5; 102:9 ^bPs 79:10; 115:2; Joel 2:17; Mic 7:10</p> <p>Psalm 42:4 ¹Or <i>move slowly with them</i> ^a1 Sam 1:15; Job 30:16; Ps 62:8; Lam 2:19 ^bPs 55:14; 122:1; Is 30:29 ^cPs 100:4</p> <p>Psalm 42:5 ¹Or <i>sunk down</i> ²Or <i>Wait for</i> ³Or <i>still</i> ⁴Some ancient versions read <i>Him, the help of my countenance and my God</i> ⁵Or <i>saving acts of</i> ^aPs 42:11; 43:5 ^bPs 38:6; Matt 26:38 ^cPs 77:3 ^dPs 71:14; Lam 3:24 ^ePs 44:3</p>	<p>Psalm 42:6 ¹Or <i>sunk down</i> ²Lit <i>Hermons</i> ^aPs 61:2 ^b2 Sam 17:22 ^cDeut 3:8</p> <p>Psalm 42:7 ^aPs 69:1, 2; 88:7; Jon 2:3</p> <p>Psalm 42:8 ^aPs 57:3; 133:3 ^bJob 35:10; Ps 16:7; 63:6; 77:6; 149:5 ^cEccl 5:18; 8:15</p> <p>Psalm 42:9 ¹Or <i>while the enemy oppresses</i> ^aPs 18:2 ^bPs 38:6 ^cPs 17:9</p> <p>Psalm 42:10 ^aPs 42:3; Joel 2:17</p> <p>Psalm 42:11 ¹Or <i>sunk down</i> ²Or <i>Wait for</i> ³Or <i>saving acts of</i> ^aPs 42:5; 43:5</p>
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Targum

Psa. 42:1 For praise, with good discernment, by the sons of Korah. ² As the deer that longs for streams of water, thus my soul longs for you, O LORD. ³ My soul is thirsty for you, for the mighty, living, and enduring God. When will I enter and see the splendor of the presence of the LORD? ⁴ My tears have become my sustenance day and night, because the enemy says to me all day, “Where is your God?” ⁵ These miracles I remember; and I will pour out the thoughts of my soul whenever I pass beneath the shelter alone; I will be strong in the camps of the righteous, [who are going] to the sanctuary of the LORD with a voice of petition and praise, a tumult of peoples coming to keep festival in Jerusalem. ⁶ Why will you be lowly, O my soul, and [why] will you rage against me? Wait for God, for again I will praise him for the redemption that is from his presence. ⁷ O God, my soul will be for me lowly, therefore I will remember you [among] those who dwell yonder in the land of Jordan, and those who dwell on the mountains of Hermoni, and the people who accepted the Torah on mount Sinai, which is lowly and small. ⁸ The upper deep calls to the lower deep, at the sound of the pouring of spouts – thus all your breakers and waves passed over me at the time we came forth from Egypt. ⁹ By day the LORD will command his goodness, and by night his praise is with me, a prayer to the God who preserves my life. ¹⁰ I will say to God my trust, “Why have you neglected me, why do I go about in darkness in the oppression of the enemy?” ¹¹ Because they kill my bones whenever my oppressors mock me, when they say to me every day, “Where is your God?” ¹² Why will you be lowly, O my soul, and [why] will you rage against me? Wait for God, for again I will praise him for the redemption that comes from his presence, for he is my God.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses are in bold.

Introduction

This psalm is the beginning of the second book of Psalms. The first forty-one psalms were attributed to David. The sons of Korach wrote the next eight hymns. Rashi said that the sons of Korach initially joined their father's infamous rebellion against Moses and Aaron. During the rebellion, the three sons realized the folly of their error and repented for their involvement. The Earth opened up and swallowed the entire assembly of Korach and sent them to Gehinnom. The LORD miraculously provided a place of refuge for Korach's three sons.

When they ascended to the Earth's surface, a Spirit of the LORD descended upon them. They prophesied the Exile of Israel, the destruction of the Temple in Jerusalem, and the advent of the Davidic monarchy. This psalm is the Song of the Day for the second day of the Sukkot festival. The Festival of the Water Drawing began on this day in the Temple.

The Festival of the Water Drawing Day - "At this most joyous season of the year, with all the electric anticipation along the caravan trails, the stirring ceremonies, and the lively singing and feasting, the epitome of celebration in Temple times took place surrounding a water ritual: the Rejoicing (*Simchat*) at the Place of (*Beit*) the Water Drawing (*Hasboavah*).

Every day of the year, after the sacrifice was burned, an offering of wine was poured on the altar. During Sukkot, there was also a water libation (*nisukh hamayim*). Some

have suggested that it was a folk rite, an inducement for rain made by pouring out water at the season's onset, transformed by the rabbis into a symbolic Temple ritual.

Each morning of Sukkot, the priests went to the pool of Siloah (Silwan) near Jerusalem to fill a golden flask. Shofar blasts greeted their arrival at the Temple's Water Gate. They then ascended and poured the water so that it flowed over the altar simultaneously with wine from another bowl. When the priest was about to pour the water, the people shouted "Raise your hand!" because of an incident that occurred in a previous year: The high priest Alexander Jannaeus (103-76 B.C.E.) showed contempt for the rite by spilling the water at his feet, a transgression for which worshippers threw their citrons at him."¹

Superscript

לְמַנְצֵחַ (lam'natzecha) – means "to who grants victory." This psalm is an appeal to the Sefirah Netzach, who offers victory. The NASB does not translate this word properly. It uses the translation "for the choir director," which is not correct.

To Him who grants victory, an instruction by the sons of Korach.

¹ Lesli Koppelman Ross, "Simchat Beit Hashoavah: The Water-Drawing Festival," My Jewish Learning, October 16, 2017, <https://www.myjewishlearning.com/article/simchat-beit-hashoavah-the-water-drawing-festival/>.

Verse One

כַּאֲזֵיל תַעֲרֹג (keearal taarog) – means “as the deer pants.” Hirsch argues that this phrase should be read as “as the deer cries.” The roe deer makes a peculiar cry. The understanding of crying comes from Joel 1:20 because of the usage of the words. Since the psalm is a cry for help, this understanding of the phrase applies to this psalm.

As the roe deer cries for the springs of water above, so my soul thirsts after You, O God.

Verse two

The psalmist distinguishes between the living God of Israel and against the “dead” idols of the nations that surround Israel.

My soul thirsts for God, for the living God and not the dead idols of the nations that surround us; when shall I come and envision myself before the countenance of God?

Verse three

Israel yearned for the LORD. It is so great that it did not feel the desire for any other kind of nourishment. Its spiritual needs were satisfied. The nation knew that it stood alone and surrounded by idol worshipers. Israel knew that she belonged to the LORD.

My tears have been my bread day and night, while the surrounding nations say, “Where is your God?”

Verse four

The nation remembers the climax of its past glory, the pilgrimage festivals, when the entire nation, gathering from all parts, wandered up to its focal point at the Temple in Jerusalem. This rallied and unified the nation.

These things I remember, and I pour out my soul within me, for I used to go along with the throng and lead them in procession to the house of God, with the voice of joy and thanksgiving, a multitude keeping festival.

Verse five

The nation needed to have courage. This verse says that hope in God is necessary for the good life.

Why are you in despair, O my soul? And *why* have you become disturbed within me? Hope in God, for I shall again praise Him *for* the help of His presence.

Verse six

Thanksgiving is offered for the Promised Land.

O my God, my soul is in despair within me; Therefore I remember You from the land of the Jordan and the peaks of Hermon, from Mount Mizar.

Verse Seven

The allegory of “floods of water” has been used in Scripture to denote pain or suffering.

Now, too, deep calls unto deep to obey your guidance; they are all Your billows and Your waves that have gone over me.

Verse Eight

The Sefirah Chesed will always shower Israel with the LORD's loving and kindness.

By the light of day, the LORD will have the Sefirah Chesed send his loving kindness, and even in the night, His song, the song of the God, is with me, a prayer for the God of my life.

Verse nine

There are times that the people of Israel thought that the LORD had forgotten them.

I say to God, my Rock, "Why would You have forgotten me? Why should I go mourning under the oppression of the foe?"

Verse Ten

The enemies of Israel were breaking their bones. The nation was helpless against its enemies.

While putting murder into my bones, my oppressors revile me, saying to me all the day, "Where is your God?"

Verse eleven

Israel discovered that there has never been a conflict between the goals set by the LORD and those toward which the nation must strive in truth. Israel will come to realize that even in the dark times, they served the LORD to advance genuine truth, happiness and fulfill the destiny that is the goal of its mission in the history of the world.

Why are you in despair, O my soul? And why have you become disturbed within me? Hope in God, for I shall yet praise Him, the help of my countenance and my God.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

As the roe deer cries for the springs of water above, so my soul thirsts after You, O God.

My soul thirsts for God, for the living God and not the dead idols of the nations that surround us; when shall I come and envision myself before the countenance of God

My tears have been my bread day and night, while the surrounding nations say, “Where is your God?”

These things I remember, and I pour out my soul within me, for I used to go along with the throng and lead them in procession to the house of God, with the voice of joy and thanksgiving, a multitude keeping festival.

Why are you in despair, O my soul? And *why* have you become disturbed within me?

Hope in God, for I shall again praise Him *for* the help of His presence.

O my God, my soul is in despair within me; Therefore I remember You from the land of the Jordan and the peaks of Hermon, from Mount Mizar.

Now, too, deep calls unto deep to obey your guidance; they are all Your billows and Your waves that have gone over me.

By the light of day, the LORD will have the Sefirah Chesed send his loving kindness, and even in the night, His song, the song of the God, is with me, a prayer for the God of my life.

I say to God, my Rock, “Why would You have forgotten me? Why should I go mourning under the oppression of the foe?”

While putting murder into my bones, my oppressors revile me, saying to me all the day, “Where is your God?”

Why are you in despair, O my soul? And why have you become disturbed within me? Hope in God, for I shall yet praise Him, the help of my countenance and my God.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

